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Effect of NAA and 2,4-D on plant regeneration from seedling leaf bases in indica rice

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Plant regeneration from indica rice is considered to be much more difficult than from japonica rice. By using a combination of 2,4-D and NAA in the medium, we obtained a high frequency of plant regeneration from indica rice. Seedling leaf bases from six indica rice varieties were used. Dehulled seeds were surface-sterilized for 5 min in 0.1% HgCl_2 solution and then washed four times in sterile water. Aseptic seedlings were raised on MS agar (0.8%) medium (pH 5.8) with 3% sucrose.

Leaf bases (1 cm long) were dissected from 7-d-old seedlings after removing the outer two leaves. Seedling leaf base explants were cultured on MS medium supplemented with 2,4-D and NAA. Cultures were kept in a growth room at 26 °C with a 16-h photoperiod of 1400 lux intensity provided by fluorescent tubes and incandescent bulbs. Preliminary experiments were conducted by culturing the seedling leaf bases of genotype CH1039 only. Explants cultured on medium supplemented with 2,4-D or NAA alone produced poor and nonembryogenic calli.

In another experimental set, both 2,4-D and NAA were added in the medium in 16 different combinations. The hormonal combination containing NAA (0.1 mg/liter) and 2,4-D (0.1 mg/liter) gave the best embryogenic callusing response in CH1039. Seedling leaf bases from five other cultivars were cultured on this medium, out of which three formed embryogenic callus. Embryogenic calli initiated from the basal portion of the leaf bases (Fig. 1a). These calli were compact, creamy, globular, and shiny (Fig. 1b). Embryogenic calli from the primary cultures were subcultured on the induction medium. After 28 d, the calli were subcultured on the same medium. Plant

Plant regeneration from embryogenic calli derived in the second subculture (MS + 0.1 mg NAA/liter and 0.1 mg 2,4-D/liter).

Cultivar	Calli plated (no.)	Regenerating calli ^a (no.)	Green plantlets produced (no.)
Chambal	46	30	124
CH1039	64	40	4534
HPU2202	64	32	342
HPU5101	44	28	158
Himadhan	60	0	-
Kaladhan	58	0	-

^a= Approximately 1 g calli (fresh weight) at the time of second subculture.

regeneration was observed in CH1039, Chambal, and HPU2202 in the first subculture (Fig. 1c).

Regenerated plantlets were counted after 35 d of the second subculture. A very high frequency of regeneration was recorded in CH1039 whereas Chambal, HPU2202, and HPU5101 had low frequencies. Himadhan and Kaladhan did not show any plant regeneration (see table). During the early stage of plantlet development, coleoptiles were seen emerging, indicating germination of embryoids (Fig. 1d).

a) Development of calli from basal portion of leaf segments; b) Embryogenic calli; c) Plant regeneration in the first subculture (cl = coleoptile); and d) High frequency plant regeneration in the second subculture.

The results indicated that genotypic variation for plant regeneration exists among different cultivars. The combination of NAA and 2,4-D in the medium influenced plant regeneration.